

الملخص

أصبحت تقنيات النطاق العريض اللاسلكية حاجة ماسة لمستخدمي شبكات الانترنت . و تعتبر أنظمة الواي ماكس احد تطبيقات تقنية النطاق العريض و التي تعمل على تردد اكبر من 2 جيجا هرتز . تقدم هذه الورقة البحثية مقترحاً لتحديد الحدود القصوى و الدنيا لفقد الاشارة نتيجة المسار و ذلك في المناطق الحضرية حيث يتم الحصول على بيانات تم إستخراجها من قياسات واقعية بإستخدام إحدى الحزم البرمجية المتخصصة ثم إستخدام إحدى طرق التحليل الرياضي و هي " تقريب أقل المربعات" لمعالجة هذه البيانات و قد تم الاستعانة بقياسات للفقد في المسار عند تردد 3,5 جيجا هرتز المستخدمه في نظام الواي ماكس و التي تم أخذها في مناطق مختلفة. تم مقارنة الحدود القصوى و الدنيا التي أقتُرحت بأحد النماذج المستخدمة في حساب الفقد في المسار لنظام الواي ماكس و الذي يُعرف بإسم نموذج SUI حيث اتضح أن هذا النموذج يقع بين الحدين الاقصى والادنى الذين تم إستنباطهما مما يعطي ثقة في ماتم إستنباطه مما يساعد مصممي شبكات الواي ماكس على تحديد حدود التغطية المتوقعة لهذا النظام.

Summary

Broadband technology has rapidly become a need for all the population. WiMAX (Worldwide interoperability for Microwave Access) is designed for broadband wireless access (BWA) that operates above 2 GHz. This paper presents a methodology for processing path loss measurement results in an attempt for calculating the bounds for the path loss using least square approximation (LSA). Use has been made of the propagation measurements at 3.5 GHz frequency band for WiMAX systems that have been taken from cells in different places. The proposed path loss bounds are compared with one of the well known models utilized in WiMAX system, namely the SUI (Stanford University Interim) model. It has been found that SUI model lies in between the proposed bounds. This gives some confidence to the proposed models. The proposed methodology with the given analysis can help designers of the network to have clear vision of the losses in such power limited system.

Path Loss Bounds for WiMAX : Concept and Analysis

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Abstract:

Broadband technology has rapidly become a need for all the population. WiMAX is designed for broadband wireless access (BWA) that operates above 2 GHz. This paper presents a methodology for processing path loss measurement results in an attempt for calculating the bounds for the path loss using Least Square Approximation. Use has been made of the propagation measurements at 3.5 GHz frequency band for WiMAX systems that have been taken from cells in different places. The proposed methodology with the given analysis can help designers of the network to have clear vision of the losses in such power limited system.

1. Introduction

Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX) is a wireless system, which is mainly based up on the IEEE standards 802.16-2004 and 802.16e-2005 for fixed and mobile applications, respectively [1]. The flexibility of wireless technology, combined with high throughput, scalability and long-range features of the IEEE 802.16 standard help to fill the broadband coverage gaps and reach millions of new residential and business customers worldwide [2]. Based upon the field measurements of signal strengths at different places, with different scenarios, path loss models have been devised. These models are used extensively in network planning, particularly for conducting feasibility studies and during initial deployment. They are also very useful for carrying out studies dealing with interferences as the deployment proceeds [7]. The widely used model, namely Hata-Okumura model, is valid for the 500-1500 MHz frequency range and there exists an elaboration on this model that extends the frequency range up to 2000 MHz (known as COST-231 Hata model). It was found that these models are not suitable for lower base station antenna heights, and hilly or moderate-to-heavy wooded terrain. To correct for these limitations, Erceg model has been introduced to cover three most common terrain categories. Erceg has devised a statistical path loss model derived from 1.9 GHz experimental data collected across the United States in 95 existing macro-cells using the least-squares linear regression on the measured path loss with distance [3]. The model tuning is an important part of the wireless network design which involves propagation model adjustments [4]. This model is the most commonly used one in WiMAX system along with the SUI channel model. Erceg model was modified in order to be used in different frequency bands (e.g. in 3.5 GHz) [5] and with different antenna heights.

All of the previously mentioned models are based upon finding a mathematical expression for the mean value of the path loss. This approach is appropriate if the variance of the filed measured is considerably small. However, if the variance is large, the model may not be suitable. In a previous paper [13], the authors have presented a methodology by which a mathematical expression for upper and lower bounds of the path loss are devised. The derivations of these bounds were based upon the analysis of some of the filed measurements of the path loss at different locations [6]. The parameters of the proposed bounds are derived using a numerical technique, namely the least squares approximation. In this paper, detailed analysis of the upper and lower bounds methodology is presented. The analysis has devised a "confidence interval" as a measure of the suitability of the proposed methodology. In addition, the methodology has been applied to other set of measurements carried out in a different location of the same frequency band (3.5 GHz). Satisfactory results have been obtained. These bounds could be suitable tools for the system designers for more precise planning of the cell coverage of WiMAX system.

2. Path Loss Bounds

Path loss can be defined as the ratio of the transmitted to received power, usually expressed in decibels. The equation for the Least Square (LS) regression analysis shows the path loss at distance d in the form [7] as:

$$L(d) = L(d_0) + 10 \gamma \log_{10} (d/ d_0) \quad (\text{dB}) \quad (1)$$

Where, d_0 is the reference point at 1 km and γ is known as the path loss exponent ($\gamma = 2$ for free space conditions). The path loss values, $L(\cdot)$ are expressed in decibels. Note that for Free Space Loss (FSL) the path loss exponent is equal to two. In the field measurements the received power is measured using the following equation. [8]

$$P_r(\text{dBm}) = P_t(\text{dBm}) + G_t(\text{dBi}) + G_r(\text{dBi}) - L(\text{dB}) \quad (2)$$

Where P_t , P_r represents the transmitted and received power and G_t , G_r represents the transmitted and received gains and L represents the path loss.

Usually, the path loss is plotted versus distance to provide a profile of signal strength up to certain ranges. Actually, the measured points on the graph are rather scattered. In order to find upper and lower bounds of these scattered points, we use suitable numerical technique. In this paper we use the Least Squares Approximation technique.

2.1. Least squares approximation

Least squares approximation which aims at minimizing the sum (over all data) of the squares of the differences between function values and data values, are most useful for large and rough sets of data. This also called linear regression where the word "linear" means that the parameters are linear [12]. In this case the path loss, we seek upper and lower boundaries of this path loss. Each boundary can be described as a straight line equation as following

$$Y = a + k X \quad (3)$$

Where "X" is value of $\log(d)$, and y is propagation path loss in (dB), and k equals 10γ . In other words:

$$L(\text{dB}) = a(\text{dB}) + 10 \gamma \log_{10}(d) \quad (4)$$

The coefficient «a» is a function of frequency and other parameters (e.g. the transmitter antenna height, the receiver antenna height). It is worth mentioning that (4) is applied for both boundaries. In order to find the value of «a» and « γ » for the upper and lower bounds, we use the least squares approximation approach making use of the measured data. In this approach, we seek the best-fit line of the measured data by minimizing the sum of the squares of the errors from this line. Using the linear regression first order model as in [12]

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

Where

β_0 and β_1 : are the model parameters

ε : is the increment of each individual Y but it is difficult to be estimated as it changes for each observation of Y . To find the parameters of (5) we shall use the least squares estimation equation as follows

$$\hat{Y} = b_0 + b_1 X \quad (6)$$

Where

\hat{Y} : predicted value of Y for given X

b_0 and b_1 : are estimates of β_0 and β_1

For n sets of observations $(X_1, Y_1), (X_2, Y_2), \dots, (X_n, Y_n)$ we can write

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \varepsilon \quad (i=1, 2 \dots n) \quad (7)$$

In this way, the sum of squares of deviation from the true line is given by:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \beta_0 - \beta_1 X_i)^2 \quad (8)$$

Where

S: called the sum of squares function

We chose b_0, b_1 for β_0 and β_1 to produce least possible value of S. To get the values of b_0, b_1 , we differentiate on S with respect to β_0 and with respect to β_1 to produce two equations then equate these two equations by zero and replace β_0 and β_1 by b_0 and b_1 . Thus we have:

$$b_0 n + b_1 \sum_{i=1}^n X_i = \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \quad (9)$$

$$b_0 \sum_{i=1}^n X_i + b_1 \sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i \quad (10)$$

The solution of equations (9) and (10) for b_1 and b_0 are given by

$$b_1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i - \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \right) \right] / n}{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right)^2 / n} \quad (11)$$

$$b_0 = \bar{Y} - b_1 \bar{X} \quad (12)$$

Where

$$\bar{X} = (X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_n) / n = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right] / n \quad (13)$$

$$\bar{Y} = (Y_1 + Y_2 + \dots + Y_n) / n = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i \right] / n \quad (14)$$

In fact, $b_0 = a$ and $b_1 = 10 \gamma$ in equation (4)

2.2. The analysis of variance:

The variance shows how much of the variation in the data has been explained by the regression technique. The variance is calculated using the Sum of Squares method is given by:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{Y}_i - \bar{Y})^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2 \quad (15)$$

Which is

$$\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of squares} \\ \text{about the mean} \end{array} \right) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of squares} \\ \text{due to regression} \end{array} \right) + \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of squares} \\ \text{about regression} \end{array} \right)$$

This shows that variation of Y's (which are the path loss in dB) can be described as the sum of two terms the sum of squares due to regression and sum of squares about the regression. In fact, the actual observations will not all lie on the regression line. However, if all observations lie on the regression line, the sum of squares about the regression (residual sum of squares) would be zero. This procedure shows how useful the regression will be as a predictor for the path loss. It would be much helpful if the sum of squares due to regression is much greater than the sum of squares about regression i.e. if the ratio R^2 of the two sums is not too far from unity, where R^2 is given by:

$$R^2 = \frac{\text{ss due to regression}}{\text{ss about regression}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{Y}_i - \bar{Y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2} \quad (16)$$

The variance R^2 is used to check a regression fit by calculating the proportion of the total variation about the mean \bar{Y} and it is often expressed in %. R^2 is a very helpful quantity that is used as a measure of how close the derived upper and lower bounds to the actual measured data obtained [12].

2.3. The confidence interval for the path loss exponent γ

The value of the path loss exponent γ has been derived from (11) where $b_1 = 10 \gamma$. However, this value may vary within certain specified interval. We can define this interval as the “confidence interval” given within the limits $\pm r$ of which value is given by:

$$r = \frac{t\left(n-2, 1-\frac{1-\alpha}{2}\right) s}{\left\{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2\right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (17)$$

Where

$t\left(n-2, 1-\frac{1-\alpha}{2}\right)$: is the critical value for t-distribution with (n-2) degree of freedom of the sum of squares about the regression and α represents the confidence limit ($\alpha < 1$) [12].

3. Data extraction

The data can be extracted from measurements results using the software package FindGraph version 1.871. This package has been used to get the data of the path loss given in [6]. A comparison between the measured and extracted data is shown in figure 1.(a and b). It is clear that the extracted data are very close to the measured ones.

Figure 1.a Urban Propagation Measurements at 3.5 GHz [6]

Figure 1.b Extracted data from the from measurements results

It is clear that the maximum distance of these measurements is 1 km. However, after we derive the upper and lower bounds equations we will extend the distance up to 5 km.

4. Data processing

Using the extracted data, this gives us as much as 240 data samples for the path loss in dB versus distance in km. We shall divide the data into a number of groups, such that each group will contain a certain number of samples within the range of measurements. This method will help us to decide the best fit values for our bounds like b_0, b_1 . This in turn affects R^2 and also the confidence interval for the

path loss exponent γ . This approach also allows the designer to have a good range of parameters selection.

4.1. The upper bound

In this subsection, the data of the upper most points of figure 1.b. are processed which contain 240 data samples. Data will be grouped into samples by taking 25 samples at each one. The average value of each group is calculated and hence we have 10 average values (table 1). The same approach will be applied by taking groups of 10 samples each, and groups of 5 samples each. Also, the whole set of samples will be taken without grouping. Table 2 gives the calculated parameters for each of the described grouping approach. Table 3 gives the confidence interval ($\pm r$) for the path loss exponent at different grouping approach.

Table 1. The 10 average values for groups of 25 each

Distance (km)	Path Loss(dB)
0.1165	102.3672
0.1527	103.0720
0.2026	106.2040
0.2655	111.3560
0.3299	120.9440
0.4196	120.5360
0.5112	129.0680
0.6451	133.3840
0.8119	137.7200
0.9689	145.3800

Table 2. The upper bound parameters for different samples

Parameter	Groups ,each with 25 samples	Groups ,each with 10 samples	Groups ,each with 5 samples	Total samples
a (dB)	98.274	97.9342	97.9572	97.9059
γ	5.13769	5.2584	5.25291	5.27005
R ² %	95.6945 %	94.6441 %	94.2224 %	94.0426 %
α	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
confidence interval %	95%	95%	95%	95%
No. of samples	10	24	48	240
Degree of Freedom	10	24	48	240

Table 3. confidence interval for the path loss exponent with different samples for upper bound

Groups ,each with 25 samples
4.24921 $\leq \gamma \leq$ 6.02618
Groups ,each with 10 samples
4.70531 $\leq \gamma \leq$ 5.81149
Groups ,each with 5 samples
4.86687 $\leq \gamma \leq$ 5.63896
Total samples
5.10031 $\leq \gamma \leq$ 5.43979

In figure 2, the upper bound of the path is plotted versus distance with the parameters obtained from table 2 for the different grouping approach. From figure 2 it is clear that the group of 25 samples is the highest one, and the group of 5 samples is the lowest one while the group of the total samples lies in between. This result shows that sometimes limited number of data can provide better regression than large number of data. As the group of the total samples is located midway among other groups we chose this one for our work as an upper bound equation model.

Figure 2. The upper bound with different samples group

Figure 3. The upper bound and the measured data

The upper bound is plotted in figure 3 with the measured upper most points of path loss, it is clear that it is close to a straight line where

$$a = 97.91 \quad , \quad \gamma = 5.27 \tag{18}$$

So the path loss equation for upper bound can be expressed as

$$L(\text{dB}) = 97.91 + 10 * 5.27 * \log_{10} (d) \tag{19}$$

This equation will be applied to other sets of measurements in next subsections as an upper bound.

4.2. The lower bound

In this subsection, we will take the data of the lower most points of figure 1.b. which contain 240 data samples. We will group the samples in the same way as in the case of the upper bound. Table 4 gives the calculated parameters for each of the described grouping approach.

Table 4. The lower bound parameters for different samples

Parameter	Groups ,each with 25 samples	Groups ,each with 10 samples	Groups ,each with 5 samples	Total samples
a (dB)	79.6565	79.1649	79.1767	78.9939
γ	3.66473	3.83351	3.83072	3.93113
R ² %	94.4273 %	92.251 %	91.6507 %	91.6620 %
α	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
confidence interval %	95%	95%	95%	95%
No. of samples	10	24	48	240
Degree of Freedom	10	24	48	240

Table 5. Confidence interval for the path loss exponent with different samples for lower bound

Groups ,each with 25 samples	
2.93888	$\leq \gamma \leq$ 4.39057
Groups ,each with 10 samples	
3.34226	$\leq \gamma \leq$ 4.32476
Groups ,each with 5 samples	
3.48758	$\leq \gamma \leq$ 4.17387
Total samples	
3.75262	$\leq \gamma \leq$ 4.05526

In figure 4, the lower bound of the path is plotted versus distance with the parameters obtained from table 4 for different grouping approaches. From figure 4 it is clear that the group of 25 samples is the highest one, the group the total samples is the lowest one while the other groups are lie in between, although the group of the total samples is the smallest. This means that it will contain any path loss data for the lower bound. As the group of the total samples covers other the different groups we chose this model for our work as

lower bound equation model. Table 5 gives the confidence interval ($\pm r$) for the path loss exponent at different grouping approach. Figure 5 shows the lower bound with the measured data.

Following the same procedure as in the case of the upper bound, we have a and γ for the lower bound given by

$$a = 78.9939, \quad \gamma = 3.93113 \tag{20}$$

So the path loss equation for lower bound can be expressed as

$$L(\text{dB}) = 78.99 + 10 * 3.93 * \log_{10}(d) \tag{21}$$

This equation will be applied to other area of measurements in next subsections as lower bound.

4.3. Estimated upper and lower bounds

Now we will use the most likely parameters estimated in the previous subsections to calculate the upper and lower bounds for the path loss (up to distance of 1.2 km) as shown in figure 6. It is also clear from the same figure that the difference between the upper and lower bounds at the small distances is small (about few dB) and the difference increases at large distances to be tens of dB. This is because the value of coefficient « a » in equation (4) is a function of frequency as well as other parameters (e.g. non line of sight conditions).

When we extend the distance from 1 km to 5 km as shown in figure 7, we note that the difference between the bounds is still large. We note that the SUI model curve still lies in between the bounds.

Figure 4. The lower bound with different sam group

Figure 5. The lower bound with measured data

Figure 6 Upper and lower bounds using least square approximation for 1 km

Figure 7 Upper and lower bounds compared with SUI model for 5 km

4.4. Applying the bounds to other area measurements

We apply the proposed upper and lower bounds to other set of measurements at the same frequency band (3.5 GHz) obtained from [11]. The bounds are plotted on the curve containing the extracted data of the set of measurements as shown in figure 8. This figure illustrates the bounds as well as the mean value of the path loss. When we apply the upper bound equation (19) and lower bound equation (21) and following same analysis we get the results shown in table 6.

Figure 8 Upper and lower bounds compared with the mean path loss

It is clear that the upper bound equation fits 61.26 % of the upper most points of figure 8. Also it is clear from the same figure that there are several points located outside the upper bound. On the other hand the lower bound equation fits 74.25% of the lower most points.

If we apply the upper and lower bounds for a third set of measurements at the frequency band 3.5 GHz as in [7], we find that our bounds are still suitable for the path loss measured in urban area as shown in figure 9.

Figure 9 Upper and lower bounds compared with measurements from [7]

Also in figure 9 it is clear that the bounds derived follow the pattern of the measured data. It can therefore be used to give an estimate of the data beyond the maximum distance of the measured data even though some of the measured points lie out of the bounds due to some differences in the urban area structure. When apply the upper bound equation (19) and lower bound equation (21) and performing same analysis we have the results shown in table 5.

Figure 9 shows how the derived regression equation fit the model. It is clear that the upper bound equation fits 56.65% of the upper most points. On the other hand the lower bound equation fit 58.11% of the lower most points.

Table 6. Parameter for upper and lower bound of figure 9

Parameter	Upper Bound
R ² %	61.2579 %
γ confidence interval	4.76137 $\leq \gamma \leq$ 5.77873
Lower Bound	
R ² %	74.2499 %
γ confidence interval	3.64291 $\leq \gamma \leq$ 4.16497

Table 7. Parameter for upper and lower bound of figure 10

Parameter	Upper Bound
R ² %	56.6512 %
γ confidence interval	3.71616 $\leq \gamma \leq$ 6.82394
Lower Bound	
R ² %	58.113 %
γ confidence interval	2.92514 $\leq \gamma \leq$ 4.88274

5. Conclusion

The path loss models available in literature are based upon formulating mathematical expressions that describe the mean value of the path loss for different propagation environments. However, the mean value will not indicate the profile of the path loss behavior at different distances especially when the variance of the data is considerably large. Depicting the upper and lower bounds of the path loss shall be useful in such case.

In this paper, mathematical expression for the path loss bounds (upper and lower) have been predicted. The parameters included in these expressions are derived from the measured data using the least squares approximation of the first order which is a numerical technique. The measured data are extracted from some filed measurements available in literature by using FindGraph package, whereas the numerical calculations are carried out using MATLAB 2008.

The upper and lower bounds have been analyzed mathematically where an expression for the variance R^2 is obtained. This is helpful in checking the fitness of the bounds of the measured data. A parameter called "confidence interval" has been derived for the path loss exponent γ . R^2 is helpful for the designers of the WiMAX networks to choose the path loss exponent.

The case of an urban area is considered where the maximum distance varies between (1-5) km with an operating frequency 3.5 GHz. The bounds obtained using the least squares approximation of the first order matches with the measured data up to the maximum distance of measurements. It is obvious that the parameters predicted in the mathematical expression for this technique will be different if operating frequency and/or the environment of the measurements vary (suburban, rural, etc.). The predicted upper and lower bounds have been applied to measured data of other two different urban areas with the same frequency band (3.5 GHz). The bounds have been found fitting the two cases.

The proposed methodology can be used to give more clear vision of the path loss profile in WiMAX system especially if the variance of measured data is large. The upper and lower bounds are not the exact boundaries; they rather give estimates of the boundaries for the path loss so that it can be used as borders to the possible maximum and minimum values of path loss. This can help designers of the WiMAX networks to have clear vision of the losses in such power limited system.

References:

- [1] A. Rial, H. Krauss, J. Hauck, and Others "EMPIRICAL PROPAGATION MODEL FOR WIMAX AT 3.5 GHz IN AN URBAN ENVIRONMENT", IEEE MICROWAVE AND OPTICAL TECHNOLOGY LETTERS / VOL. 50, NO. 2, February 2008, Pages (483 – 487)
- [2] D. Luca, F. Fiano, F. Mazzenga, and Others "Outdoor Path loss models for IEEE 802.16 in suburban and campus-like environments", IEEE ICC 2007, VOL. 24 , Issue 28, Pages (4902-4906)
- [3] Vinko Erceg, , Larry J. Greenstein, Others "An Empirically Based Path Loss Model for Wireless Channels in Suburban Environments" IEEE JOURNAL ON SELECTED AREAS IN COMMUNICATIONS, VOL. 17, NO. 7, JULY 1999
- [4] Zerihun Abate "WiMAX RF System Engineering", Artech House, 2009, VOL.17, Issue 7, Pages (161-163)
- [5] T.S. Chu, Larry J. Greenstein, Others "A Quantification of Link Budget Differences Between the Cellular and PCS Bands" IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON VEHICULAR TECHNOLOGY, VOL. 48, NO. 1, JANUARY 1999, VOL. 48, Issue 1, Pages (60 - 65)
- [6] Marcus C. Walden, Frank J. Rowsell, "Urban Propagation Measurements and Statistical Path Loss Model at 3.5 GHz", 2005, Pages (363- 366) VOL. 1A
- [7] V.S. Abhayawardhana, I.J. Wassell, D. Crosby and Others "Comparison of Empirical Propagation Path Loss Models for Fixed Wireless Access Systems", IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference, 2005, VOL. 1 Pages (73- 77)
- [8] Winton Afric1, Branka Zovko Cihlar, Sonja Grgic "Methodology of Path Loss Calculation using Measurement Results", IEEE 2007 VOL.27, Pages (257 – 260)
- [9] Tamara A. Carter, Richard A. Tapia and Anne Papakonstantinou "Linear Algebra-An Introduction to Linear Algebra for Pre-Calculus Students ", Rice University, May1995. Pages (95- 106)
- [10] Mohamed Ouweis Kabaou, others "Path Loss Models Comparison in Radio Mobile Communication", Medwell Journals 2008, Pages (628-632)
- [11] A. Valcarce Rial1, Harald Krauss, Joachim Hauck, and others "EMPIRICAL PROPAGATION MODEL FOR WIMAX AT 3.5 GHz IN AN URBAN ENVIRONMENT", IEEE Microwave and Optical Technology Letters, February 2008 VOL. 50, Issue 2, Pages (483 – 487)
- [12] Norman R. Draper, Harry Smith, "Applied Regression Analysis-Third edition", John Wiley 1998, Pages (1-5,15-45)
- [13] Mohamed Ali Aboul- Dahab, Hossam Mohamed Kamel, "Methodology for Calculating Path Loss Upper and Lower Bounds for WiMAX", accepted and presented at the "IEEE third International Conference on New Technology, Mobility and Security (NTMS) ", 20-23 Dec. 2009, Cairo, Egypt.